

Analysis of Limiting Control Rod Patterns in the BWR Power Range

Alexey Cherezov^{1,*}, Victor Fournier¹, Alexander Vasiliev¹, Jiri Dus², Hakim Ferroukhi¹

¹Paul Scherrer Institute, Forschungsstrasse 111, Villigen, 5232, Aargau, Switzerland;

²Swiss Federal Nuclear Safety Inspectorate, Industriestrasse 19, Brugg, 5200, Aargau, Switzerland

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ABSTRACT

The boiling water reactor (BWR) startup process includes withdrawing control rods from the core to achieve criticality and reach the nominal power rate. The control rods are withdrawn sequentially according to the Banked Position Withdrawal Sequence (BPWS) list of rules, which limits the movement of control rods to minimize the reactivity increment in a potential control rod drop accident event. However, the BPWS rules allow a large number of withdrawal sequences, and thus a lot of control rod patterns can be observed during startup. This work aims to identify the distribution of permitted limiting patterns associated with large reactivity increments that should serve as an input for conservative Control Rod Drop Accident (CRDA) analysis. In this study, about 10 billion control rod patterns have been evaluated by an artificial neural network to screen potentially limiting patterns, which are then verified by a full-core analysis steady-state code SIMULATE-3. The proposed method enables fast identification of limiting patterns, providing an efficient tool for assessment of the BWR safety during startup.

Keywords: BWR, BPWS, CRDA, CNN, SIMULATE-3

1. INTRODUCTION

The control rod withdrawal sequence of Boiling Water Reactors (BWRs) consists of two consecutive ranges: startup and power. These ranges are associated with the control rod density defined as the amount of withdrawn control rods to the total amount of control rods in reactor core and varying from 0 to 100% of All-Rods-Out (ARO). As there is the elementary step of rod movements, which is equal to 1/48 of the rod elevation in this study and called a *notch*, the amount of control rods is measured in terms of the number of notches rather than the number of rods. The startup range varies from 0 to 50% ARO and it starts from the control rod pattern where all rods are inserted to the “black-and-white” pattern where approximately half of the rods are inserted. The power range varies from 50 to 100% ARO, and it practically finishes when 20% of rated power is achieved. The startup range of the withdrawal sequence was investigated at the cold zero-power (CZP) operating conditions in [1]. This work continues the startup range analysis to the power range by performing the main analysis at the CZP operating conditions, and then reassessing the results at the Hot Zero Power (HZP) states.

The primary goal of this study is to evaluate a large number of control rod patterns that may occur in the BWR startup, and identify those of the patterns where the Control Rod Drop Accident (CRDA) simulation results are the most severe. According to the regulatory requirements, the black-and-white pattern at 50% ARO is conservative enough to be considered for the CRDA analysis. However, as this study demonstrated, a plenty of even more conservative patterns can be observed, in which the reactivity increments caused by the drops are larger, and, thus, the CRDA results are potentially more severe. Moreover, the distribution of patterns across withdrawal steps and control rod positions is investigated that may help to predict the conservative patterns for other reactor core cycles.

*alexey.cherezov@psi.ch

The control rod withdrawal procedure adheres to the Banked Position Withdrawal Sequence (BPWS) to restrict rod movements and, thus, minimize the increment reactivity due to a hypothetical control rod drop. It is assumed, that any partially or fully withdrawn rod within a given pattern can initiate a CRDA, and that such a rod can drop between arbitrary initial and final axial positions but not below the position at which the drive mechanism was stopped, see the details in [1, 2]. In this study, we are focused on the analysis of *limiting* control rod patterns, where the increment reactivity exceeds the threshold $\Delta\rho^*$ established by a regulatory body.

The occurrence of limiting patterns is very low, accounting for about 0.001% of the permitted patterns. Therefore, a lot of computational effort is required to identify a large number of limiting patterns. To reduce computational costs, a Convolution Neural Network (CNN) was developed [2] to relate control rod patterns to reactor core reactivity. Then, the CNN is used to screen rapidly a set of randomly generated patterns and to select the potentially limiting patterns followed by the verification using the full-core analysis code SIMULATE-3 [3]. The CNN is trained and validated on reference reactivities calculated by the same code, with adjustment by a constant criticality bias observed from comparison with criticality measurements of the reactor. The search is performed at the Cold Zero-Power (CZP) operating conditions at the end of cycle and with zero concentrations of Samarium and Xenon isotopes for conservative reasons. Then, the identified limiting patterns are evaluated at the HZP operating conditions.

2. METHODOLOGY

In this section, we describe the control rod sequences and patterns permitted by BPWS, neural network architecture and training procedure, and its accuracy on the training and limiting patterns.

2.1. Startup Procedure

There are 149 control rods distributed across 45 gangs, which are arranged into 10 groups. Thus, each control rod refers to a certain group and gang at the same time. There are two arrangements of gangs and groups, referred to as Sequence A and Sequence B. The movement of the rods is restricted by the BPWS system in such a way that no rod can be moved until all rods in the current gang and/or group have been driven to the current bank position. As a rule, the control rods are moved one-by-one within a gang first, and then, the gangs are moved one-by-one within a group. However, depending on a withdrawal step, another control group can be started before the previous was finished. The number of possible control rod patterns depends on specific BPWS rules and gang/group arrangements. The design of BWR control rods is detailed in [4], the BPWS withdrawal rules for startup range are detailed in [1], and for the startup and power ranges in [5] and [6]. However, the specific arrangement is not disclosed in this study by proprietary reasons.

Fig. 1 shows the increment of the reactor reactivity in the startup process from 0 to 100% ARO. The reactor reactivity increases with amount of withdrawn rods from a deeply subcritical state through the critical point at the 25% ARO where $k_{eff} \approx 1$ to the black-and-white pattern at the 50% ARO to the state of 20% of the nominal power where almost all rods are withdrawn.

The first and second phases of the startup range involve control rod movements in full-mode and bank-mode, respectively. These movements are highly constrained by the BPWS system, resulting in a relatively small number of permitted configuration, on the order of $\sim 10^5$ patterns in phase 1 and $\sim 10^6$ patterns in phase 2. These patterns can be evaluated using the direct computations by a full-core analysis code in a reasonable term. However, when inoperable control rods are taken into account, the number of possible patterns explodes, making it necessary to employ a fast-working tool, such as a CNN, as demonstrated for the startup range analysis in [1].

For the power range, the selection of groups and gangs to withdraw is much more flexible under the

BPWS, resulting in an astronomical number of possible patterns of at least $\sim 10^{40}$. Note, that this assessment is based on combinatorial formulas and on the actual distribution of rods across groups and gangs, which cannot be disclosed in this study by proprietary reasons. However, the strategy of such the assessment was presented in Appendix C of [1].

Figure 1. Reactor reactivity increase during the control rod withdrawal process evaluated under the CZP operating conditions for Sequence A and Sequence B. Here 10^n denotes the approximate number of patterns permitted by the BPWS system for each withdrawal phase. There are three phases: 1 - withdrawal of the first pair of groups in the full-mode; 2 - withdrawal of the second pair of groups in the bank mode until the black-and-white pattern; 3 - withdrawal of the remaining six groups until 20% of the nominal power is achieved.

Given the enormous complexity of this problem and the extremely low occurrence of limiting patterns within the possible set, the use of a CNN becomes very necessary to assess the most conservative control rod pattern where the largest increment due to the rod drop is observed. Note, that the traditional CRDA analysis considers only the black-and-white pattern as it is thought to be the most conservative case. However, using the the neural network approach, it becomes feasible and relatively inexpensive to evaluate a large number of control rod configurations and find much more conservative patterns, thus contributing to the safety analysis of BWR cores.

2.2. Architecture

The CNN shown in Fig. 2 receives a control rod pattern at the input in the form of a (15,15)-array, and produces the corresponding multiplication factor k_{eff} , as output. The input pattern contains 149 control rods at different axial positions ranging from 0 to 48 notches, that is from the fully inserted to the fully withdrawn states, correspondingly. The internal processing includes two convolutional layers with (2,2)-kernels and 64 and 16 channels, followed by a flattening layer, which contains no trainable parameters, and three fully connected (dense) layers with 512, 256, and 128 neurons. The ReLU activation function is applied to all layers. The total number of trainable parameters is 1 553 745. The same architecture was employed in the previous study [1], since it was found optimal for both startup and power ranges.

2.3. Training Procedure

The training dataset was generated through direct simulation of control rod withdrawal steps from 50% to 100% ARO. In total, 2000 withdrawal sequences were produced. For instance, Fig. 3 shows the distribution of the training patterns of Sequence A across reactor reactivity and withdrawal banks (graphics

Figure 2. Architecture of CNN used for prediction of reactor multiplication factor under CZP operating conditions for a given control rod pattern.

for Sequence B look similar). As can be seen, the dataset contains two types of patterns referred to the initial and final state of the drop events. The amount of permitted event patterns grows exponentially over withdrawal step as more and more control rods were moved and become susceptible to CRDA. To ensure a uniform distribution of patterns across withdrawal steps, only 40 randomly selected patterns per sequence and 4 drop events per pattern were included into the training dataset. The total number of patterns generated for Sequences A and B combined 390,000. Evaluation of these patterns by the SIMULATE-3 full-core analysis code required a total computation time of 54 CPU-days. The training dataset generation details are presented in [2].

The dataset was divided into two subsets: 80% for training and the remaining 20% for testing. The mean-square error loss function and Adams optimization method were used during the training. A batch size was set to 256. The loss function reached 10^{-5} after about 100 epochs and it required of about 1 hour on NVIDIA's 802 GeForce GTX 1080.

The reactivity increments predicted by CNN are inaccurate due to approximation errors, and, therefore, some of the limiting patterns cut on a certain threshold are turned-out to be non-limiting after the SIMULATE-3 verification. On the other hand, some of the trial patterns processed by CNN and predicted to be non-limiting may turn-out to be limiting after the verification. Thus, there exists two subsets of patterns in the trial set, which refer to over-predicted and under-predicted cases. To maximize the number of verified limiting patterns, it is beneficial to adjust the threshold in such a way that the fraction of under-predicted patterns is minimum. It, however, increases the amount of the over-predicted patterns and associated computational costs for full-core code verification - this increase is tolerable to some extent as the occurrence rate of the limiting patterns is very low. Therefore, in this study, the threshold was set to 475 and 480 pcm for Sequence A and Sequence B, respectively, to guarantee the under-prediction rate within 0.1%. The over-prediction fractions of the limiting patterns for Sequence A and B are 26.2% and 19.4%, respectively. The detailed analysis of the over- and under-prediction rates and its dependence on the threshold is presented in [2].

The performance of the CNN was evaluated on the training dataset and on the set of found limiting patterns. The random sampling method for training data construction guarantees under-representation of the patterns observing large reactivity increments - this is why the CNN performance degrades on the limiting patterns, as can be seen in Fig. 4. These graphics show the distribution of the predicted control rod worth (CRW) residuals versus the CRW values calculated by SIMULATE-3. As can be seen, the standard deviations σ_A and σ_B are 2 pcm for the training dataset for both Sequence A and Sequence B,

with zero biases μ_A and μ_B . For the set of limiting patterns, the residuals are larger but still relatively small compared to the CRW values, with $\sigma_A = 12 \text{ pcm}$ and $\sigma_B = 9 \text{ pcm}$.

The limiting patterns identified at this stage can be also included into the training dataset to improve the quality of CNN predictions. Specifically, we added 20,000 limiting drop events of each Sequence A and Sequence B, thus increasing the training dataset by approximately 10%. After retraining, the new subset of limiting patterns was produced using CNN and verified against SIMULATE-3. The performance of the retrained model is presented in Table I. While the reduction in CRW errors on the training patterns is negligible, a significant improvement is observed on the limiting patterns after the model update.

Figure 3. Left: distribution of the training patterns of Sequence A across reactivity $\rho = 1 - 1/k_{eff}$ given in pcm and withdrawal banks given in % ARO. Right: distribution of the initial and final (event) patterns of the drop events for the same training dataset across reactor multiplication factor k_{eff} .

Figure 4. The residuals of CRWs predicted by CNN and calculated by SIMULATE-3 for the training patterns and the limiting patterns.

Table I. Mean value μ and standard deviation σ of the CNN predictions from SIMULATE-3 measured in pcm. The asterisk indicate the discrepancies after the CNN retraining.

Sequence	Training Patterns				Limiting Patterns			
	μ	σ	μ^*	σ^*	μ	σ	μ^*	σ^*
A	~ 0	2.1	-0.1	2.0	1.0	12.0	-0.2	4.3
B	~ 0	2.2	-0.1	2.1	-2.2	8.9	-0.3	5.5

3. RESULTS

In this section, we discuss the results of the CNN-based analysis of the limiting control rod patterns, including their occurrence rates, distributions and the feedback effect.

3.1. Occurrence

In total 7.8 billion patterns were generated and evaluated by CNN for Sequences A and B under the BPWS rules, as can be seen in Table II. From them, 458,000 potentially limiting patterns (SLP) have been selected and verified by SIMULATE-3. The number confirmed limiting patterns (CLP) is equal to 372,000. The total processing time of the limiting patterns, including CNN evaluations and verification, amounted to 67 CPU-days. This does not include the generation of the training dataset, which required approximately 35 CPU-days.

The fraction of withdrawal sequences containing at least one limiting pattern is denoted by LS, and the fraction of the limiting rod drops across all possible drop events is denoted by LD. As can be seen, the limiting sequence occurs relatively often, while the limiting drop events are extremely rare. At the same time, Sequence B demonstrates much larger risk of limiting events compared to Sequence A.

Table II. Occurrence of limiting patterns, sequences and drop events.

Sequence	Total	SLP	CLP	LS	LD	CPU-days
A	4.3B	113K	85K	12%	0.001%	27
B	3.5B	345K	287K	35%	0.005%	40

The distributions of control rod events and patterns found by the ANN-based approach were analyzed with respect to the positions of the dropped control rods and the position within the withdrawal process. The results indicate that the limiting events are primarily associated with drops of peripheral control rods - a feature also observed in the startup range analysis [1]. In addition, an asymmetry in the distributions was observed towards the south-east and south-west quarters of the reactor core due to the asymmetrical distribution of bundle exposures at the end of the reactor cycle. A key difference between the distributions is that the limiting events in the power range are concentrated in a few control rod positions, whereas those in the startup range are more evenly distributed across the control rod positions.

3.2. Feedback effects

The limiting control rod patterns are to be used for the downstream CRDA simulations under the CZP operating conditions as required by conservative reasons for the licensing analysis. However, when the temperature feedback is taken into account, the reactivity increments due to rod movements decrease; hence, most of the limiting patterns disappear. It is expected that the reactivity increments calculated

for the hot zero power (HZP) operating conditions are always less than that for the CZP state. In order to see the effect of the fuel and coolant temperature feedback, we re-evaluated the control rod drop reactivity effects for three different operating conditions:

- Inlet temperature $T_{in} = 100^\circ\text{C}$ and rated power $P = 0\%$.
- Inlet temperature $T_{in} = 200^\circ\text{C}$ and rated power $P = 0\%$.
- Inlet temperature $T_{in} = 286^\circ\text{C}$ and rated power $P = 0.3\%$.

The rated core flow rate for all cases is the same, $G_{in} = 30\%$. Fig. 5 compares these three operating conditions to the CZP state with $P = 0\%$ and $T_{in} = 20^\circ\text{C}$ with zero concentrations of Samarium and Xenon isotopes. The computed CRWs are corrected on about +10 pcm if the Samarium model is included.

Figure 5. The effect of the inlet temperature T_{in} and the rated core power P on the distribution of CRW of the limiting events found in Sequence A and Sequence B.

As was expected, the CRW significantly reduces with the inlet temperature increase followed by the decrease in the coolant density and neutron moderation in the coolant. The CRW of only few patterns remains above 500 pcm threshold for the second operating conditions. For the last case when the power is non-zero, the core-average fuel temperature for all cores is nearly equal to the coolant inlet temperature. However, the local distribution of the power and fuel temperature varies in a wide range, following by the radial power peaking factor about 2.8, which results in the stronger Doppler effect at the places where there control rods are not inserted.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study presents the analysis of control rod patterns occurred in the BWR startup within the BPWS rules. The increment reactivities of the control rod drops were assessed for each control rod pattern using a CNN shown in Fig. 2. The amount of patterns is very large, therefore, a fast-working method is required to assess many of them - this is why the neural network approach is employed. The *limiting patterns* whose increment reactivity exceeds a certain threshold were re-evaluated by the full-core analysis code SIMULATE-3 and selected for further CRDA simulations using licensing tools. This analysis is performed for the power range of the control rod withdrawal sequence featuring a large number of permitted patterns, and complements the recent analysis done for the startup range presented in [1].

In this study it was confirmed that the CNN of the same architecture is efficient for the power range of the withdrawal sequence, demonstrating prediction accuracy within 12 pcm for the limiting patterns, as can be seen in Fig. 4 and Table I. This uncertainty is similar to what was observed for the startup range [1].

The effect of the power and temperature feedbacks on the increment reactivity of the limiting patterns was assessed by full-core analysis code SIMULATE-3. It has been shown that the limiting patterns are effectively disappear at the HZP state indicating core safety under realistic operating conditions.

However, the identified limiting patterns are essential for the reactor core licensing analysis anyway, because this analysis is performed at the CZP state by conservative reasons, and for the black-and-white pattern at 50% of ARO. There are limiting patterns observing larger increment reactivity than that of the black-and-white pattern. Therefore, using these limiting patterns for CRDA will make the safety analysis even more conservative. It should be noted, that this work was initiated and supported by the Swiss Nuclear Safety Inspectorate (ENSI). The ongoing work is to incorporate the methodology of the current analysis into the licensing procedure of Swiss BWRs.

NOMENCLATURE

<i>ANN</i>	Artificial neural network
<i>ARO</i>	All rods out
<i>BPWS</i>	Banked position withdrawal sequence
<i>BWR</i>	Boiling water reactor
<i>CNN</i>	Convolution neural network
<i>CRDA</i>	Control rod drop accident
<i>CRW</i>	Control rod worth
<i>CZP</i>	Cold zero power
<i>HZP</i>	Hot zero power

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